

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Integrating the Application of TikTok in Teaching Physical Activities Towards Health and Fitness

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Abstract

Objectives: This research aims to identify the effect of TikTok on learning dance in Physical Education of the 2nd year college students in one state University and colleges (SUCs) in Iloilo, Philippines. **Methods:** This study used a one-group pretest-posttest design with 30 items of questionnaires as an instrument to evaluate the effect of TikTok on learning dance in Physical Education to 2nd-year college students in Western Visayas, Philippines. The statistician used the following tests: data frequency distribution at certain rating levels. Further, on testing hypothesis N, the T-test was conducted. **Findings:** More than 40% of the total number of learners gained scores between the 1-6 and 7-12 ranges. The pre-test result showed that the learners got an overall mean of 10.0000, and the level of performance was fair. The findings exposed more than 80% of students who gained scores between the 19-24 and 25-30 ranges. The result was described as "Very Good." The results of the T-test analysis revealed a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test. The results showed that TikTok dramatically affects students' performance in Physical Education focused on Social Dance, Ballroom Dancing, or Dance Sports. **Novelty/Applications:** The use of social media apps is recommended and faculty are encouraged to become innovators in improving the curriculum. There is an increasing need for teachers to be competitive with current trends as students today are tech-savvy.

Keywords: TikTok; Social Dance; Physical Education; College Students; Western Visayas; State Universities and Colleges (SUCs)

1 Introduction

During the past decades, the Philippine basic education system shifted to the K12 Basic Education Program, adding two years in senior high school (SHS). There was a disruption in the implementation of tertiary education for two years. The higher education institutions (HEIs) also revised their curriculum by deleting some subjects similar to SHS. However, in the study about the readiness of SHS graduates to enter

college, they were defined as needing to be equipped. Thus, the results suggest looking into the policy, like curriculum alignment, admission guidelines, and involvement in preparing graduates for university life⁽¹⁾. Readiness is essential for SHS graduates. In addition, there were many factors involved from 2016 until the present. There was a pandemic, and the curriculum shifted to another teaching mode, and students were caught unaware. Another factor is online learning, which requires gadgets and connectivity. In the Philippines, not all students can afford gadgets, and the availability of internet connections. Social media also plays a vital role in this technological era. Many children are on social media almost 24 hours every day. Thus, this study specifically focused on Physical Education and TikTok.

One problem nowadays on social media is the excessive use by younger generations. Adults are clamouring because most children and adolescents are into social media applications such as Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and many more. This study will use social media as instructional materials for Northern Iloilo, Philippines, university students. There were studies about social media worldwide, but not on these selected students. This innovation could be a good avenue to understand social media as a trend.

1.1 Objective of the Study

The main objective of this research is to identify the effect of TikTok on learning dance in Physical Education of the 2nd year college students in one state University and colleges (SUCs) in Iloilo, Philippines.

1.2 Significance of the Study

This study aims to connect social media to teaching and learning courses in HEIs. The study's results will help stakeholders make social media an essential tool in the teaching and learning process. Also, educators can find alternative solutions for teaching strategies. And for students to utilize something that they use 24 hours every day. This process is a win-win solution for educators and students.

1.3 Literature Review

1.3.1. Higher Education in the Philippines

In the Philippines, state universities and colleges (SUCs) provide a quality education through effective and efficient faculty profiles. Each SUC in the region offers the best educational practices, strategies, and methods to make students globally competitive and well-versed in terms of skills and knowledge in their specific field of interest⁽²⁾. The implementation of the current basic education curriculum has evolved into different names, but the focus is to help students become mentally, physically, and emotionally healthy. The HEIs have adapted various innovations from research to teachers' functions. For instance, the respondents were critical officials in a study about best practices in research engagement in HEIs, delivering financial support, credit load, and training⁽³⁾. Further, another study exposed various designations, inadequate facilities, and a need for more knowledge about online learning⁽⁴⁾. Many things have happened to the tertiary education system in the Philippines to make it globally competitive.

1.3.2. Innovative approaches in teaching Higher Education

COVID-19 has changed the landscape of the education system in the Philippines; HyFlex is the new game. Innovation is the key to today's generation of higher education learning. However, this depends on students' capabilities. Adopting this type of innovation required financial support among students. In the Philippines, most cannot buy gadgets or internet connections. Nevertheless, similar to international education, Filipinos have similar concepts on the effectiveness of online learning on students' performance⁽⁵⁾. But above all, teaching is not all about technology as a trend; an innovative approach that affects students' interest and academic performance should also be adopted. But it so happens that in today's generation, technology is the trend.

1.3.3. Physical Education as a General Subject in HEIs

The implementation of Physical Education in the SUCs in the country is taken from DECS Order no. 58, s. 1990, containing the regulations and requirements for the College Service Physical Program or CSPE⁽⁶⁾. Physical Education is not only a course but a program that will help students' mental health and well-being through physical activities⁽⁷⁾. The physical education curriculum should contain applicable learning activities. Regular physical activities not only help develop physical health but also mental health. One study exposed that physical fitness is the main element of physical education because it implies a learning range of motor skills and abilities. Additionally, doing physical activities like exercise assists in promoting different organs in the body⁽⁸⁾.

Thus, it was confirmed by another researcher that it is critical to execute physical exercises and activities frequently⁽⁹⁾. Hence, physical education is a crucial part of students' education because it contributes to many beneficial effects.

In the 21st century, the Physical Education curriculum is not a separate program but an integrated one that focuses on health-related fitness and the development of physical expertise. Before, the curriculum was more focused on sports skills and athleticism. But through rigorous research works it was found that activities that have health benefits are significant for the physical demands of daily life. Physical Education is designed to endorse the development of students' physical, social, and mental health through selected physical activities. Physical Education is composed of three functions: biological, integrative, and social. One of the objectives of Physical Education is social development; hence, dance is one of the activities for the development of necessary social traits⁽¹⁰⁾. There are two types of dances taught in college Physical Education, Physical Education 113, which is Folk Dance, and Social Dance in the course outline "Principles of Motor Control and Learning of Exercise, Sports, and Dance." But this study is only focused on dance, specifically performed during the lesson like the social dance. Dance is an art form where the body moves, such as walking, or clapping in a pattern, to a particular rhythm rhythmically through the beat of the music.

1.3.4. Dance as one of the Lessons in PE in HEIs

Research reviewing dance interventions exposed a positive effect on the participants. It has various effects on different age levels; for children to adolescents, the benefits are physique-related perceptions, personality, confidence, self-expression, and perception of dance abilities. And for adults, self-expression, self-efficacy, personality awareness, self-development, and self-confidence. But the findings suggest going for more studies, such as having many participants⁽¹¹⁾. Furthermore, the mental and emotional benefits of dance are improved mental stamina and memory, enhanced self-confidence, self-expression, emotion, attaining goals, and being ready for challenges⁽¹²⁾. Thus, many experts today have ventured into different research integrating concepts of dance.

1.3.5. Social Media as Instructional Material

TikTok, which is the most popular social media worldwide, has limited integration in education is still limited. But TikTok has become a popular mode of instruction in education that could impact teaching and learning processes⁽¹³⁾. TikTok hosts a diverse range of short videos or films of music, dances, short stories, and others that can be a good source of instructional materials in education. Based on the results, 61% of the participants used TikTok 3 times a day, 59% of them watch fun videos on this social media, and 33% used this platform for education. Furthermore, according to findings, 79% learned new knowledge, 82% using TikTok think the knowledge learned was practical and useful. Also, 68% responded that using TikTok was better than traditional methods⁽¹⁴⁾. Thus, this study used TikTok in teaching physical education in higher education in the Philippines.

There were many interventions used in terms of dance engagement. Such as the use of technologically supported learning, the results showed a positive effect on students' learning⁽¹⁵⁾. This also confirms that dance researchers and policymakers change the landscape of dance research by using technological materials. With the proliferation of social media, young dancers are already employed on online platforms, and this already has vague implications for the field of dance.

Smartphone applications were also used in one study for physical activities, and the results were effective because they helped secondary PE teachers promote physical activity for adolescents⁽¹⁶⁾. Many students use smartphones to navigate social media.

1.3.6. TikTok to Teach PE

And the social media application TikTok is already in demand for content creators like younger dancers. One retracted study reported that almost 95% of the respondents wanted interactive technologies compared to traditional teaching methods in learning social dances⁽¹⁷⁾. Thus, social media was utilized in this study, specifically, music found on TikTok, because young generations go gaga over what they hear and see. Everyone must follow the trends and easily memorize and downloaded in the technology application. In Jakarta, physical education teachers in elementary, junior high school, and senior high school use TikTok because it attracts students' attention. Still, limited features are the backlash of this type of social media⁽¹⁸⁾.

One study showed that the primary purpose of students watching TikTok was to feature body transformation, fitness tips, and motivational content. Also, they applied exercise tips and nutrition education that are essential to daily life⁽¹⁹⁾.

1.4 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on social dance, commonly called ballroom dancing or dance sports. Ballroom dancing has a great effect on human cognitive function and a healthy brain⁽²⁰⁾. Ballroom dancing deflected from the colonization of Western countries like France, Britain, and America to East and Southeast Asia during the early twentieth century. Social dances have

different types but are included under the umbrella of ballroom dance⁽²¹⁾. Even in the Philippines, ballroom or dance sports are always part of academic institutions' activities. One implication of the study was an improvement in social and emotional intelligence, such as *self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship skills*⁽²²⁾. Thus, having ballroom dancing makes everyone unwind from busy and hectic daily activities.

2 Methodology

2.1 Research Design

This study employed a one-group pretest-posttest design to determine the effect of TikTok teaching dance in Physical Education to 2nd -year college students in state universities and colleges (SUCs) in the Philippines. A qualitative part was added to ensure novelty in the results of the study. The design is purely an interview of all the participants.

2.2 The Subject

The study participants were 35 Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management 2nd year students at Northern Iloilo State University, Victorino Salcedo Campus, Sara, Iloilo, Philippines, during the academic year (AY) 2022-2023. These students were taking up PathFit 3 or the Rhythmic Activities. These students were selected because they were students of one of the researchers. No disruption of classes will occur. The faculty can integrate the lessons into the conduct of the study.

2.3 Research Instrument

A researcher-made test with thirty (30) items in multiple-choice format as the instrument for this study was developed with the validation of experts and teachers teaching Physical Activities. An open-ended guide questionnaire was formulated for the qualitative part. Each of the participants joined the said interview.

2.4 Data Collection Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the school administrator and the respondents to conduct the study. The said study did not interfere with the usual classroom operations because the research was connected to the participants' lessons. This is to make teaching and learning dance fun and exciting because almost all the students use TikTok in their free time.

2.5 Intervention

The intervention of this study was different videos related to Rhythmic Activities taken from TikTok. The researchers selected 15 videos on folk dance, ballroom dancing, jazz exercise, and Zumba. The researchers showed the video clips to the students during their classes.

2.5.1. Phase I. Negotiation with the Students

The researchers ask permission from the 2nd-year college students enrolled in PathFit3 to be the subjects of this research study. Upon the agreement of the students, the researchers explain the mechanics of the study.

2.5.2. Phase II. Establishing the Baseline Data

The researchers gave a 30-item multiple-choice type of test to the students as the pre-test focused on the Rhythmic Activities.

2.5.3. Phase III. Intervention Period

The researchers presented and explained the interventions to the 35 participants of the study. The researchers used the selected video clips during class as instructional materials in learning Rhythmic Activities. From the video clips shown to them, they follow the dance steps and sometimes they innovate during the practical exam.

2.5.4. Phase IV. Evaluating Results for Intervention

The researchers administered a post-test to investigate the effectiveness of using TikTok in learning dance in Physical Education.

2.5.5. Data Analysis Procedure

The study used a quantitative method in analysing and reporting the gathered data using non-descriptive statistics in the treatment of the data. Specifically, frequencies and percentage computation are used to determine data frequency distribution at certain rating levels. The data that will be gathered will be compiled, sorted out, organized, tabulated, and subjected to statistical treatments to facilitate the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data.

2.5.6. Statistical Tools

The gathered data was compiled, sorted out, organized, and tabulated. It was subjected to a statistical treatment to facilitate data presentation, analysis, and interpretation. The statistician used the following tests: data frequency distribution at certain rating levels. Further, on testing hypothesis N, the T-test was conducted.

2.5.7. Scoring and Quantification of Data

Table 1 shows the scoring, mean percentage Score (MPS), and descriptive rating.

Table 1. Score, MPS, and Descriptive Rating

Score	MPS (%)	Descriptive Rating
25-30	81-100	Excellent
19-24	61-80	Very Good
13-18	41-60	Good
7-12	21-40	Fair
1-6	1-20	Poor

3 Results and Discussion

Table 2 shows the pre-test performance of the students before the intervention of the application of TikTok.

Table 2. Pre-test Performance of the Participants Before the Intervention

<i>Before Intervention</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>MPS (%)</i>	<i>Description</i>
Pre-test	35	10.0000	2.70	21-40	Fair

Table 2 shows that more than 40% of the total learners gained scores between the 1-6 and 7-12 ranges. The pre-test result showed that the learners got an overall mean of 10.00, and the level of performance was fair. The results are attributed to the fact that the students, upon taking the pre-test, may have retained basic knowledge of information regarding the competencies. The pre-test results showed that students need to learn about integrating the popular social media app TikTok in learning Rhythmic Activities

Just like using M-gym Media to study Rhythmic Activities in Universitas Negeri Medan’s Faculty of Sport Science showed 70% of students during pretest have weak knowledge of rhythmic abilities⁽²³⁾.

However, one study about TikTok in PE also showed that not all students know or use the application. Many, or around 85%, stated that TikTok is better than other social media apps. Most said the TikTok application could be used in academic activities⁽¹⁸⁾. Thus, before using TikTok in lectures, teachers must conduct surveys and encourage students to register on the app because it will be used in the lesson as a teaching and learning strategy.

Table 3 represents the post-test performance of the students after the intervention of the TikTok application.

Table 3. Post-test Performance of the Students After the Intervention

<i>After Intervention</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>MPS (%)</i>	<i>Description</i>
Post-test	35	21.94	2.30	61-80	Very Good

The findings exposed more than 80% of students who gained scores between the 19-24 and 25-30 ranges. The post-test result showed that the students got an overall mean of 21.94, and the level of performance was very good, which means that all students excelled, passed the test, and mastered the learning competencies. All of these students gained scores of 19.

Thus, the results during the post-test showed that 86.7% indicated that many of them were TikTok users before using the interventions⁽²⁴⁾. The TikTok application focuses on 21st-century skills. Also, social media enhances connections within the

classroom community. TikTok provides emotional security, especially for highly anxious students; thus, it "makes everyone feel like they belong"⁽²⁵⁾. Likewise, even a study about learning regular verbs showed that integrating TikTok helped improve students' performance tremendously⁽²⁶⁾. Also, in a survey about writing skills in PE, out of 36 students, nine strongly agreed, ten agreed, and seven were neutral. With the results. TikTok has the potential to enrich students' curiosity⁽²³⁾. Also, with intervention using M-gym Media, the results increased to 83%⁽²³⁾. As long as the intervention is effectively implemented, students' performance increases exponentially.

Table 4 displays the significant difference in the pre-test and post-test performance of the students before and after the intervention.

Table 4. Showing the significant difference in the pre-test and post-test performance of the students before and after the intervention of the instructional material

	Mean	SD	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Pre-test – Post-test	-11.94	2.57	-27.53	34	.000	"Reject the Null Hypothesis"

The results of the T-test analysis revealed a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test. The analysis yielded a mean of -11.94286 at an SD of 2.56610 at a T-value of -27.534 and Sig. (2-tailed) .000 P<0.05 significant difference. The null hypothesis in the study is rejected. Studies have revealed no significant difference between TikTok and other variables. Nevertheless, consumption and engagement have a significant relationship⁽¹⁶⁾.

Figure 1 shows the qualitative part of the study. There were 6 categories asked about in the interview. Category 1 is about whether they have TikTok. Category 2 is about whether they use their TikTok. Category 3 is if TikTok is interesting. Category 4: TikTok can be used as instructional materials in PE. Category 5 is about looking for music. Category 6 is about dance steps.

Fig 1. Responses of Students on the TiKTok as materials in teaching PE

On the results, half of the respondents had no TikTok account, and not all who had TikTok used the application.

One respondent said, "I am OK with other social media applications like Facebook and YouTube."

Another said, "I registered on TikTok because my friend has it, but I don't use it often."

The majority say yes, that TikTok is interesting. Another respondent said, "TikTok because it has almost all the features I needed: music, dance, communicate with friends, and online shopping."

Thus, both for use as instructional materials to look for music and dance steps, all say yes to the potential of TikTok in enhancing the tertiary curriculum, specifically PE.

Young people use digital technologies almost everywhere⁽²⁷⁾. Thus, technology has a diverse purpose in human existence, like in education. Furthermore, there was a study showing the emerging acceptance of utilizing TikTok as a pedagogical tool in Physical Education, around 28% were willing to use this social media as instructional materials. Also, 52% agreed, and 48% totally agreed to incorporate dance-based activities taken from TikTok-inspired movements⁽²⁸⁾. TikTok-assisted instructional

materials enhance motivation and participation among students. Also, it helps students improve performance and mitigate mental-health issues. But needed more mechanisms for overexposure on the use of this social media ⁽²⁹⁾.

4 Conclusions

Based on the pre-test and post-test results, this study concludes that using social media apps like TikTok significantly helped students learn social dancing or ballroom dancing. Teachers are encouraged to become innovative in every teaching and learning engagement. As a 21st-century educator, including technology in the curriculum is crucial. Students nowadays are tech-savvy. Even though not all students have TikTok accounts, students still use the application as instructional materials in PE. TikTok has potential benefits for education. However, proper guidance is required. Learning institutions should not prohibit the use of social media in school but should encourage educators to make it worthwhile for academic purposes. However, similar studies must be conducted in another course to ensure the novelty of the results. Also, not only dance but also some other lessons are used to back up the claims that TikTok is indeed instructional material. But a specific mechanism must be created for the effective implementation of these innovative approaches. For instance, TikTok is only allowed during class hours as instructional materials. Since internet connectivity is free to all, regulation is recommended. We all know that students today are more exposed to social media and often spend most of their daily time in front of their gadgets.

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